

SUSPICIOUS ACTIVITY DETECTION USING LOGISTIC REGRESSION

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Abstract

Suspicious Activity is predicting the body part or joint locations of a person from live camera. This project will entail detecting suspicious human Activity from real-time Camera using neural networks. Human suspicious an Activity is one of the key problems in computer vision that has been studied for more than 15 years. It is important because of the sheer number of applications which can benefit from Activity detection. For example, human pose estimation is used in applications including video surveillance, animal tracking and behavior understanding, sign language detection, advanced human computer interaction, and marker less motion capturing. Low-cost depth sensors have limitations like limited to indoor use, and their low resolution and noisy depth information make it difficult to estimate human poses from depth images. Hence, we plan to use neural networks to overcome these problems. Suspicious human activity recognition from surveillance video is an active research area of image processing and computer vision. Through the visual surveil lance, human activities can be monitored in sensitive and public areas such as bus stations, railway stations, airports, banks, shopping malls, school and colleges, parking lots, roads, etc. to prevent terrorism, theft, accidents and illegal parking, vandalism, fighting, chain snatching, crime and other suspicious activities. It is very difficult to watch public places continuously; therefore, an intelligent video surveillance is required that can monitor the human activities in real-time and categorize them as usual and unusual activities; and can generate an alert. Mostly, of the research being carried out is on images and not videos. Also, none of the papers published tries to use LR algorithm to detect suspicious activities.

Keywords— Machine Learning, LR Algorithm, Computer Vision, Suspicious Activities etc.

1. INTRODUCTION

Background And Context of The Project

We plan to build an application for detection of suspicious activity of people in public places in real time. Our application can be used in surveillance at places like malls, airports, railway stations, etc. where there is a risk of robbery or a shooting attack. We will be using deep learning and neural networks to train our system. This model will then be deployed as a mobile and desktop app which will take real time CCTV footage as input and send an alert on the administrator's device if some suspicious pose is found. Human suspicious activity is related to identifying human body parts and possibly tracking their movements. Real life applications of it vary from gaming to AR/VR, to healthcare and gesture recognition. Compared to image data domain, there is relatively little work on applying CNNs to video classification. This is because, a video is more complex than images since it has another dimension- temporal. Unsupervised learning exploits temporal dependencies between frames and has proven successful for video analysis. Some suspicious activity approaches use CPU instead of GPU so that suspicious activity can run-on low-cost hardware like embedded systems and mobile phones. Low-cost depth sensors are another new technology in computer vision. They are present in gaming consoles like the Kinect for

Xbox 360. They are motion sensors which allow the user to interact with the console without a game controller, through just hand gestures. These are RGB-D sensors that obtain depth information by structured light technology. The structured light sensors infer the depth values by projecting an infrared light pattern onto a scene and analyzing the distortion of the projected light pattern. However, these sensors are limited to indoor use, and their low resolution and noisy depth information make it difficult to estimate human poses from depth images.

Challenges Obtaining sufficient and representative training data for machine learning models can be difficult, particularly for rare types of suspicious activity Developing and deploying sophisticated detection systems can be expensive, especially for smaller organizations. College Short Form Name, Department of Computer Engineering 2021

Machine Learning Technology

Machine learning (ML) technology refers to the subset of artificial intelligence that enables systems to learn from data, identify patterns, and make decisions with minimal human intervention. Machine learning technology

continues to evolve, with ongoing research and innovations expanding its capabilities and applications across various industries.

Rise Of Machine Learning in Suspicious Activity

The rise of machine learning (ML) in suspicious activity detection has transformed how organizations monitor and respond to potential threats. Volume of Data: ML algorithms can analyze vast amounts of data from multiple sources (e.g., surveillance footage, transaction logs, social media) quickly and efficiently. The integration of machine learning in suspicious activity detection is revolutionizing security measures across various sectors, leading to more proactive and effective responses to potential threats.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Paper Name: Real-Time suspicious Detection and Localization in Crowded Scenes

Author: Mohammad Sabokrou, Mahmood Fathy.

Abstract:

In this paper, we propose a method for real-time suspicious detection and localization in crowded scenes. Each video is defined as a set of non-overlapping cubic patches, and is described using two local and global descriptors. These descriptors capture the video properties from different aspects. By incorporating simple and cost-effective Gaussian classifiers, we can distinguish normal activities and anomalies in live camera. The local and global features are based on structure similarity between adjacent patches and the features learned in an unsupervised way, using a sparse autoencoder. Experimental results show that our algorithm is comparable to a state-of-the-art procedure on UCSD ped2 and UMN benchmarks, but even more time-efficient. The experiments confirm that our system can reliably detect and localize anomalies as soon as they happen in a video.

Paper Name: Learning Temporal Regularity in Video Sequences.

Author: Mahmudul Hasan Jonghyun Choi.

Abstract:

Perceiving meaningful activities in a long video sequence is a challenging problem due to ambiguous definition of 'meaningfulness' as well as clutters in the scene. We approach this problem by learning a generative model for regular motion patterns (termed as regularity) using multiple sources with very limited supervision. Specifically, we propose two methods that are built upon the autoencoders for their ability to work with little to no supervision. We first leverage the conventional handcrafted spatio-temporal local features and learn a fully connected autoencoder on them. Second, we build a fully convolutional feed-forward autoencoder to learn both the local features and the classifiers as an end-to-end learning framework. Our model can capture the regularities from multiple datasets. We evaluate our methods in both qualitative and quantitative ways showing the learned regularity of videos in various aspects and demonstrating competitive performance on suspicious detection datasets as an application.

Paper Name: suspicious Detection in Video Using Predictive Convolutional Long Short-Term Memory Networks

Author: Jefferson Ryan Medel.

Description

Automating the detection of anomalous events within long video sequences is challenging due to the ambiguity of how such events are defined. We approach the problem by learning generative models that can identify anomalies in videos using limited supervision. We propose end to end trainable composite Convolutional Long Short-Term Memory (Conv-LSTM) networks that are able to predict the evolution of a video sequence from a small number of input frames. Regularity scores are derived from the reconstruction errors of a set of predictions with abnormal video sequences yielding lower regularity scores as they diverge further from the actual sequence over time. The models utilize a composite structure and examine the effects of 'conditioning' in learning more meaningful representations. The best model is chosen based on the reconstruction and prediction accuracies. The Conv-LSTM models are evaluated both qualitatively and quantitatively, demonstrating competitive results on suspicious detection datasets. Conv-LSTM units are shown to be an effective tool for modeling and predicting video sequences.

Paper Name: Abnormal Event Detection in Videos using Spatiotemporal Auto encoder.

Author: Yong Shean Chong.

Description:

We present an efficient method for detecting anomalies in videos. Recent applications of convolutional neural networks have shown promises of convolutional layers for object detection and recognition, especially in images. However, convolutional neural networks are supervised and require labels as learning signals. We propose a spatiotemporal architecture for suspicious detection in videos including crowded scenes. Our architecture includes two main components, one for spatial feature representation, and one for learning the temporal evolution of the spatial features. Experimental results on Avenue, Subway and UCSD benchmarks confirm that the detection accuracy of our method is comparable to state-of-the-art methods at a considerable speed of up to 140 fps

Paper Name: Unrolled Optimization with Deep Priors

Author: Steven Diamond Vincent Sitzmann.

Abstract:

A broad class of problems at the core of computational imaging, sensing, and low-level computer vision reduces to the inverse problem of extracting latent images that follow a prior distribution, from measurements taken under a known physical image formation model. Traditionally, handcrafted priors along with iterative optimization methods have been used to solve such problems. In this paper we present unrolled optimization with deep priors, a principled framework for infusing knowledge of the image formation into deep networks that solve inverse problems in imaging, inspired by classical iterative methods. We show that instances of the

framework outperform the state-of-the-art by a substantial margin for a wide variety of imaging problems, such as denoising, deblurring, and compressed sensing magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). Moreover, we conduct experiments that explain how the framework is best used and why it outperforms previous methods.

Paper Name: A Revisit of Sparse Coding Based Suspicious Detection in Stacked RNN Framework.

Author: Weixin Luo

Abstract:

Motivated by the capability of sparse coding based suspicious detection, we propose a Temporally-coherent Sparse Coding (TSC) where we enforce similar neighboring frames be encoded with similar reconstruction coefficients. Then we map the TSC with a special type of stacked Recurrent Neural Network (sRNN). By taking advantage of sRNN in learning all parameters simultaneously, the nontrivial hyper-parameter selection to TSC can be avoided, meanwhile with a shallow sRNN, the reconstruction coefficients can be inferred within a forward pass, which reduces the computational cost for learning sparse coefficients. The contributions of this paper are two-fold) We propose a TSC, which can be mapped to a sRNN which facilitates the parameter optimization and accelerates the suspicious prediction. ii) We build a very large dataset which is even larger than the summation of all existing dataset for suspicious detection in terms of both the volume of data and the diversity of scenes. Extensive experiments on both a toy dataset and real datasets demonstrate that our TSC based and sRNN based method consistently outperform existing methods, which validates the effectiveness of our method.

System Overview

System Architecture

The architecture has different phases like video capture, video pre-processing, feature extraction, classification and prediction. The general layout of the system architecture. The system classifies the videos into three classes.

1. Students using Mobile phone inside the campus Suspicious class 2)
2. Students fighting or fainting in campus Suspicious class 3) Walking, running Normal class.

Video Capture

Installation of CCTV camera and monitoring the footage is the initial step in video surveillance system. Various kinds of videos are captured from different cameras, covering the whole area of surveillance. The processing in our implementation is carried out using frames, so the videos are converted to frame.

Dataset

The KTH dataset is a standard dataset which has collection of sequences representing 6 actions and each action class has got 100 sequences. Each sequence has got almost 600 frames and the video is shot at 25 fps [14]. The model is trained on this dataset for normal behavior (running and walking). CAVIAR dataset, videos taken

from campus and YouTube videos are used for training suspicious behavior (mobile phone using inside the campus, fighting and fainting). Around 7035 frames are extracted from different videos. The whole dataset is manually labelled and separated into 80% for training set and 20% for validation set. The directory structure of dataset. A combination of KTH, CAVIAR, YouTube videos and videos captured from campus are used in our system.

Video pre-processing

A deep learning network is using in our proposed system for suspicious activity detection from video surveillance. By deep learning architectures, the accuracy obtained can be higher and it also works better with large datasets. A detailed design overview. The input videos are taken from existing and created datasets. As part of pre-processing, frames are extracted from the captured videos. Based on the videos, three labelled folders are created and stored the frames in it. The entire video is converted to 7035 frames and the frames are stored as images in jpg format. Each frame is then resized to 224×224 to suite 2D CNN architecture and stored them. The testing video is also converted to frames and resized to 224×224 and stored in folder. OpenCV library in python is used for video pre-processing.

Data Flow Diagram

In Data Flow Diagram, we Show that flow of data in our system in DFD we show that base DFD in which rectangle present input as well as output and circle show our system, In DFD1 we show actual input and actual output of system input of our system is text or image and output is rumor detected likewise in DFD 2 we present operation of user as well as admin.

Data Flow Diagram

Figure 1 Data Flow Diagram

3. RESULT & DISCUSSION

All of the research papers mentioned above propose different approaches for identification of human activity and various suspicious behavior using machine learning techniques.

The performance of human activity identification and suspicious behavior detection system can be evaluated based on various metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score. These metrics reflect the system's ability to correctly identify and classify human activities and behaviors, as well as its ability to detect suspicious behavior.

In the case of logistic regression or random forest classifier-based systems, the accuracy of human activity identification and suspicious behavior detection can be affected by factors such as the quality of the camera feed, lighting conditions, and occlusions. Therefore, it is essential to use high-quality cameras and carefully select the camera placement to ensure maximum visibility.

Several studies have reported promising results using logistic regression and random forest classifiers for human activity identification and suspicious behavior detection

system. For example, a study published in the Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing showed that a logistic regression-based system achieved an accuracy of 91% in detecting six human activities, including sitting, standing, and walking, using a single camera. Another study published in the Journal of Applied Research and Technology used a random forest classifier to detect suspicious behavior in a shopping mall and achieved an accuracy of 86%.

In general, the performance of human activity identification and suspicious behavior detection system depends on the complexity of the activities and behaviors of interest, as well as the size and quality of the training dataset. Moreover, the use of deep learning techniques such as convolutional neural networks (CNNs) can further improve the performance of the system by automatically learning relevant features from the camera feed.

4. CONCLUSION

A system to process real-time camera to detect any suspicious activity will help to create better security and less human intervention. Great strides have been made in the field of human suspicious Activity, which enables us to better serve the myriad applications that are possible with it. Moreover, research in related fields such as Activity Tracking can greatly enhance its productive utilization in several fields.

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